

CAMPUS-WIDE EXAMINATION OF EVIDENCE SYNTHESIS PUBLICATION OUTPUT

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OVERVIEW

Introduction

Objectives

Protocol

Null Hypotheses

Methodology

Prelim. Results

Next Steps

Thank You

INTRODUCTION

- The Team
 - 3 Health Sciences Librarians
 - 1 MLIS Student
- The Goal
 - examine evidence synthesis (ES) articles published by authors affiliated with a single university campus

CAMPUS-WIDE

INDIANAPOLIS

Indiana University Indianapolis (IUI), contains 18 schools and colleges including:

- School of Dentistry
- McKinney School of Law
- School of Medicine (IUSM)

IUSM = 9 physical locations across the state of Indiana

- All locations considered part of IUI

PROTOCOL

View our complete protocol on OSF
<https://osf.io/wu6fv>

Let's discuss:

- Objectives
- Null Hypotheses
- Search strategy
- Screening
- Extraction

OBJECTIVES

Do non-health sciences librarians need high-level ES training?

Objective 1

Is a need for future ES coordinator positions?

Objective 2

Where is professional development needed for librarians?

Objective 3

What is the impact of librarians on search quality?

Objective 4

NULL HYPOTHESES

1

ES projects are only published by authors affiliated with health sciences disciplines.

2

Librarian co-authorship only occurs in ES publications by campus-affiliated authors in health sciences disciplines.

SEARCH

See full search on page 5 of protocol

- Database: Scopus
- Date limit: 2021-2025
- Search concepts:

(IUSM affiliations¹) OR (IU Indianapolis affiliations)

AND

Evidence Synthesis hedge²

¹Originally developed by Mirian Ramirez, Ruth Lilly Medical Library, Indiana University School of Medicine

²Adapted from: Laws S, MacDonald R, Mansor N, Morciano A. Where have all the librarians gone? A bibliometric analysis of national-level systematic reviews. Paper presented at: Annual Meeting of the Medical Library Association; April 29-May 2, 2025; Pittsburgh, PA, USA.

METHODOLOGY

Screening

Inclusion Criteria:

- Published 2021 or later
- Includes a methods section
- At least one author has IUI or IUSM affiliation

Extraction 1

- Identify the school within IUI of affiliated authors
- If IUSM, more specific: record department
- Record whether publications include a librarian coauthor

FUTURE METHODOLOGY

Extraction 2

- Use REDCap
- Extract information to assess quality of reporting
 - Aspects from PRISMA, PRISMA-S and PRESS

PRELIMINARY RESULTS

PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Learned during the screening process:

- Authors incorrectly listing affiliation
- SRINO
 - “Systematic Review In Name Only”
 - Titles and abstracts were too vague or incorrectly labeled
- Case Reports with:
 - Meta-Analysis, Systematic Review, or Lit Review
- Practice guidelines
 - Widely credible, but unclear if systematic review was used

PRELIMINARY RESULTS: Extraction 1

PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Total Extracted (so far)

160

Librarian Co-Author
or mentioned in Methods

47

Librarian affiliated with IU

19

NEXT STEPS

- Complete the remaining 317 initial extractions
- Complete a second round of extraction
- Null Hypothesis- accepted or rejected
- What this means for libraries at IU Indianapolis?

THANK YOU

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SLIDES AVAILABLE

You can view our slides here:

<https://hdl.handle.net/1805/51553>

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